

(see table). On flooded soil the root system was compact and developed horizontally. The roots were spread like a thick mat all over the superficial soil layers.

In the saturation regimes the rice

plants developed vertical root growth. Water roots or nodal roots that started at panicle initiation were absent but appeared in the flooded regimes.

The deep brown color of roots in the saturation regime may have been caused

by the formation of ferric compounds that coat root surfaces under oxidized conditions. The flooded regime favors the accumulation of ferrous compounds around the root surface and causes a light brown color. ■

Effects of foliar spray of *Azotobacter chroococcum* on rice

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Azotobacter chroococcum occurs in the phyllosphere of water hyacinth *Eichhornia crassipes*. The presence of *Azotobacter* spp. in the phyllosphere of several field crops, vegetables, and ornamental plants has been reported. An attempt was made to determine how the phyllosphere bacterium *A. chroococcum* that occurs with water hyacinth affects the rice crop.

The field experiment was conducted in a randomized block design with four replications in 1977–78 samba (Sep–Jan). A pure culture of *A. chroococcum* (phyllosphere bacterium of water hyacinth) was obtained from the

Effect of foliar spray of *A. chroococcum* on grain and straw yield of rice.^a Tamil Nadu, India.

Treatment	Grain yield		Straw yield	
	t/ha	Increase over control (%)	t/ha	Increase over control (%)
0–50–50kg NPK/ha	1.4	–	4.1	–
0–50–50kg NPK/ha + <i>Azotobacter</i> spray	1.7	7.6	4.5	9.0
50–50–50kg NPK/ha	2.2	37.3	5.6	36.4
50–50–50kg NPK/ha + <i>Azotobacter</i> spray	2.3	42.9	5.6	36.4
50–50–50kg NPK/ha + topdressing of 50 kg N/ha	2.4	49.6	6.8	63.6

^a Differences significant at 5% level. Grain yield: SE = 0.102. C.D. = 0.315. Straw yield: SE = 0.56. C.D. = 1.73.

Indian Agricultural Research Institute, New Delhi. The bacterium was grown in Jensen's nitrogen-free medium. The variety ADT31 was grown in a 5 × 4-m plot with various fertilizer treatments, both with and without *Azotobacter* spray. The rice plants were sprayed 3 times with a foliar spray of the *Azotobacter* culture suspension at 100 ml/m² (16 × 10⁸ cells/ml) on the 15th, 30th, and 45th day after

transplanting.

The foliar *Azotobacter* spray significantly increased grain and straw yields. The plots treated with 0–50–50 kg NPK/ha + *Azotobacter* spray yielded 7.6 and 9.0% more grain and straw, respectively, than the unsprayed plots (see table). Plots treated with 50–50–54 kg NPK/ha + *Azotobacter* yielded about the same as the unsprayed plots. ■

Azolla as a nitrogen source for rice in northeast Thailand

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The use of *Azolla pinnata* as a substitute for nitrogen fertilizer in rice was evaluated in a field trial. The experiment

was in a randomized complete block with four replications. Azolla was seeded at 312.5 kg/ha. Phosphorus was applied in solution with a watering can, and potassium was applied basally. Yield increases attributed to azolla were comparable to those attributed to applied nitrogen (see table). The treatment where azolla was incorporated into the soil after transplanting and that where it

was not were equally effective. Yields were similar when azolla was seeded before or after transplanting. One crop of azolla supplied at least 37.5 kg N/ha, equivalent to about 200 kg/ha of ammonium sulfate. ■

Response of RD7 rice to azolla and chemical fertilizers, Ubon Ratchathani Rice Experiment Station, 1979 dry season.

Azolla ^a	Treatment			Azolla fresh wt ^b (t/ha)	Rice yield ^c (t/ha)
	Fertilizer (kg/ha)				
	N	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O		
0	0	25	25	0	2.3 b
0	18.5 + 18.5 ^d	25	25	0	3.4 a
Seeded after T	0	12.5 + 12.5 ^e	25	17.4	3.7 a
Seeded after T	0	12.5 + 12.5 ^e	25	18.1 ^f	3.7 a
Seeded 26 DBT	0	12.5 + 12.5 ^e	25	15.1 ^f	3.5 a

^a T = transplanting. DBT = days before transplanting. ^b 20 days after seeding (DS). ^c Any 2 means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^d Split at T and panicle initiation. ^e Split just after seeding and 10 DS. ^f Incorporated 20 DS.

Correction of zinc deficiency in direct-seeded rice

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Zinc deficiency in rice seedlings is common in Louisiana. It is usually corrected with a foliar application of zinc (Zn-EDTA). But stands of small seedlings are reduced severely before farmers recognize the deficiency and